

Phytochemical-Mediated Anxiolytic and Antidepressant Effects via Modulation of Neuroplasticity in Experimental Rodent Models

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Abstract:

Background

Phytochemical-rich medicinal plants have gained considerable attention for their potential role in managing neuropsychiatric disorders. Traditional medicinal systems have extensively used various parts of *Aconitum ferox* for the treatment of multiple ailments, including rheumatism, epilepsy, and as a sexual tonic. Emerging evidence suggests that plant-derived bioactive compounds can modulate neural plasticity, thereby reducing anxiety and depressive symptoms.

Objective

The present study aimed to evaluate the anxiolytic and antidepressant potential of the ethanolic crude extract of *Aconitum ferox* based on its traditional medicinal usage and phytochemical composition.

Methods

The aqueous methanolic extract of *Aconitum ferox* was prepared using a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure. Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed to identify the major bioactive constituents. The anxiolytic activity was assessed using behavioral models, including the light–dark exploration test, elevated plus maze (EPM), rota-rod test, and actophotometer. Antidepressant activity was evaluated using the forced swim test and tail suspension test. Experimental animals were administered oral doses of 200, 300, and 500 mg/kg of the extract, and their behavioral responses were compared with control groups.

Results

Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of multiple bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and polyphenols. Treatment with *Aconitum ferox* extract produced a significant, dose-dependent increase in head dipping behavior and time spent in the open arms of the elevated plus maze and the illuminated compartment of the light–dark box. Additionally, a marked reduction in immobility time was observed in both the forced swim and tail suspension tests, indicating significant antidepressant activity ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The findings of the present study demonstrate that *Aconitum ferox* possesses significant anxiolytic and antidepressant properties, potentially mediated through modulation of neuroplasticity and neurotransmitter pathways. However, further investigations are warranted to isolate, characterize, and validate the specific bioactive compound(s) responsible for these pharmacological effects.

Graphical Abstract:

Graphical abstract created from biorender.com

Keywords: Anxiolytic activity, Antidepressant effect, Neuroplasticity, Oxidative stress, Phytochemical profiling, Behavioral models.

Introduction:

The most prevalent mental illness, anxiety is characterized by an uneasy, hazy sense of worry or concern that affects about one-fourth of people at some point in their lives of the six primary forms of anxiety disorders, generalized anxiety disorder (GAD)¹ is most common, per the Diagnostic & Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition, Text Revision (DSM-IV-TR). Despite being viewed as a singular clinical identity, depression is actually a collection of several diseases², each with its own description, typical symptoms, diagnostic standards, and course of therapy.³

A low mood or a lack of enthusiasm for routine tasks are the signs for depression as well, that are accompanied by one to four different signs of depression, including changes in appetite or weight, difficulty concentrating, exhaustion, sleeplessness, and thoughts of suicide. Depressive disorder is usually defined in terms of major depressive disorder.⁴ According to current research, there is no known cure to both anxiety or depression, with multiple treatments being available. Recurrence of depression is another issue with its therapy. These illnesses have long existed, as many botanicals have been explored as treatments. Due to the low cost of plants' very effective medications, about 74% of those in earth currently utilize them to cure a variety of ailments and conditions.⁵

One may think of herbal remedies as complementary or alternative therapies. Plant-based medicine research has progressed worldwide, demonstrating the medicinal effectiveness of many plant species in diverse animal models⁶ with the aim of finding novel compounds that may be helpful in treating neurological disorders. That is also true for the great majority of herbal medicines whose potential for use in psychotherapist was assessed in a range of animal models. These studies have provided important insights into the development of novel, extracted active phytoconstituents and medicinal plants' pharmacotherapies⁷.

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the possible anxiolytic & depressive effects of Asian medicinal herbs, particularly those originating in India, as the northern side of the region has a more varied plant flora.⁸ Based on its traditional use by the people living in the northern Himalayan region, *Aconitum ferox*, sometimes referred to as "Bachnag," was chosen. Many pharmacological effects of the plant, including antioxidant, acetylcholinesterase inhibitory,⁹ tyrosinase inhibitory, α -amylase inhibitory, and α -glucosidase inhibitory activity, have been investigated professionally. Investigating this plant scientifically may lead to more affordable and efficient ways to treat sadness and anxiety.¹⁰

Material & Method:

Plant material:

Proper collection and accurate identification of *Aconitum ferox* are essential to prevent adulteration and ensure reliable results for further studies. The plant should be collected during its flowering stage or when leaves are fully developed, documenting the precise collection point with details on geographic location, elevation, and habitat conditions. Verification of taxonomic characteristics such as leaf shape, flower morphology, and growth habit is crucial to distinguish *Aconitum ferox* from similar species or varieties. Collecting representative parts including leaves and, if possible, seeds is necessary for comprehensive herbarium preparation, ensuring detailed labeling with scientific name, collection date, and habitat description facilitates precise identification and supports botanical research efforts effectively.

Preparation of extract:

A 227.66-gram sample of the dried, coarsely ground medication was placed into a Soxhlet device and defatted with petroleum ether at 40–60°C until total defatting was obtained. When a drop from the thimble did not leave an oily mark on the filter paper, complete defatting was verified.¹¹ A few drops of the extract let dry in a watch glass to make sure the solution had evaporated and no residue remained. This process was used to verify the completion of each extraction. After being dried, the marc from the ethanol extraction was macerated with water for a full day.¹²

Chemical: The investigation employed pure, research-grade substances. Sigma-Aldrich in the United States provided the chemicals, which included diazepam.

Drug: All of the dosages of diazepam, and plant extract *Aconitum ferox* were made or given as 5 mg/kg orally & 200, 300, 500mg/kg.

Phytochemical screening:

Determination of Alkaloids:¹²

Mayer's Test: The presence of alkaloids is indicated by the production of a white and yellow precipitate if a test liquid mixes in Mayer's reagent, this is a potassium mercuric iodide solution.

Dragendorff's Test: An orange-red precipitate is observed as alkaloid are added to the test sample by using Dragendorff's reagent, that is a blend of iodide of potassium & bismuth nitrate.

Wagner's Test: When Wagner's reagent (an iodine solution) is added to the test solution, it produces a dark or reddish-brown precipitate that suggests the presence of alkaloids.

Hager's Test: Hager's reagent, a saturated form of picric acid, if treated with the sample solution yields a distinctive crystalline precipitate that indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Determination of Glycosides: ¹³

Raymond's Test: A characteristic crystalline precipitate that signifies a presence of alkaloids develops after Hager's reagent—a saturation form of picric acid—is utilized on the tested solution.

Killer-Killani Test: Combine two milliliters of the extract with one drop of a 5% ferric chloride (FeCl₃) solution, then gradually stir in one milliliter of concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). A reddish-brown hue that appears where the two liquid layers converge and the top layer turning bluish-green indicate the existence of the compound.

Determination of Carbohydrates: ¹⁴

Molisch's Test: pour a few drops of α -naphthol solution (20% in ethyl alcohol) to 2-3 ml of the extract, and then cautiously pour 1 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) along the test tube's side. The development of a violet ring at the intersection of the two liquids indicates the presence of carbs.

Fehling's Test: Nach neutralizing the extract with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and heating it with dilute hydrochloric acid (HCl), Fehling's solutions A and B are added next. The appearance of a brick-red precipitate indicates the presence of reducing sugars.

Benedict's Test: After adding an equivalent amount of Benedict's reagent to the extract, stir the mixture and let it sit for five minutes. The solution becomes green, yellow, or red when reducing sugars are present; this depends on the sugars' concentration.

Determination of Tannins: ¹⁵

Vanillin-HCl Test: Vanillin-HCl reagent (made by mixing 1 g vanillin, 10 ml alcohol, and 10 ml strong hydrochloric acid) should be mixed with the extract. The development of a pink or red tint indicates the presence of phenolic chemicals.

Gelatin Test: Add an aqueous solution of gelatin to the extract solution. The presence of tannins is confirmed by the formation of a white-buff-colored precipitate.

Determination of Steroids: ¹⁶

Liebermann-Burchard Test: Add 1-2 ml of acetic acid, 2 drops of concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) from the test tube's side, and chloroform to 2 ml of the extract. A color shift that goes from red to blue to green indicates the presence of sterols and triterpenoids.

Salkowski Reaction: Combine 2 milliliters of the extract, 2 milliliters of chloroform, and 2 milliliters of concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). Give the mixture a good shake. If the chloroform layer becomes red and the acid layer fluoresces greenish, then sterols and triterpenoids are present.

Determination of Proteins and Amino acids

Biuret Test: To 3 ml of the extract, add 4% sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and 2–3 drops of 1% sulfuric acid solution. An appearance of red or violet colouring suggests the existence of protein or peptides.

Precipitation Test: Blend the extract using 100% pure alcohol. When a white precipitate forms, it shows a presence of particular atoms, like protein or polysaccharides.

Ninhydrin Test: After 10 minutes, warm the solvent or the ninhydrin reagent on a bath of hot water. When peptide or amino acid chains are present, a violet hue appears.¹⁷

Determination of Resins:¹⁸

1. Color Detection with Ferric Chloride: Add a few drops of ferric chloride (FeCl₃) solution to the extract and alcohol mixture. Greenness is a sign that phenolic chemicals are present.

2. Turbidity Test: To create an extract solution, dissolve 2 g of the drug in 5 ml of distilled water after it has been dissolved in methanol. Turbidity is an indication that certain chemicals, including saponins, are present.

Determination of Flavonoids:

Lead Acetate Test: After dipping a filter paper strip into the extract's alcoholic solution, wash it with ammonia solution. The filter paper's color changing from white to orange signifies the presence of flavonoids.

2. Shinoda Test: Stir in 5 milliliters of 95% alcohol, a few drops of strong hydrochloric acid (HCl), and 0.5 grams of magnesium turnings after mixing the extract first. The emergence of a pink hue indicates the presence of flavonoids.

TLC Analysis of Plant Extract:

The drug extract was prepared by dissolving it in a few drops of methanol in an Eppendorf tube and mixing it well. Using a capillary tube, the sample solution was spotted onto the TLC plate along the line drawn 2 cm from the bottom. The mobile phase was prepared by mixing ethanol and chloroform in the desired ratio and was poured into a developing chamber, which was then covered.¹⁹

The TLC plate with the spotted sample was placed in the developing chamber, ensuring that the bottom edge (below the sample spots) was immersed in the mobile phase. The mobile phase was allowed to ascend the plate until it reached the line drawn 1 cm from the top. The TLC plate was then removed from the chamber and left to dry completely. For visualization of the spots, the dried TLC plate was placed in an iodine chamber for 10-15 minutes.

Infrared (IR) spectroscopy

IR spectrum is analyzed to identify characteristic absorption bands or peaks. These observed absorption bands are matched with known IR spectra from databases or literature to identify the functional groups and chemical bonds present in the sample. Absorption bands are assigned to specific vibrational modes of chemical bonds, such as C-H stretch or O-H bend, based on their position and intensity. Tables no.1 of characteristic absorption frequencies for common functional groups aid in peak identification. If quantitative analysis is required, the concentration of specific components in the sample is quantified using calibration curves or peak area measurements²⁰

Experimental Animals

A facility dedicated to pharmacology research at Aryakul College of Pharmacy and Research in Lucknow was home to a male Wistar rat. Animals were housed in conventional laboratory settings (12 hours of light and dark at $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), fed standard mouse pellets, and given unlimited access to water. Study protocols were followed to in line to the Ethical Committee.

Acute Toxicity Assay

Acute toxicity tests were conducted in accordance with Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) guidelines. Five sets of five male wistar rats (weighing 200–250 g) each were created. Every rat was monitored & its baseline behavioral data were noted. The experimental animals were given unlimited access to water throughout their one-night fast. Three groups of rats were given *Aconitum ferox* plant extract at dosages of 200, 300, and 500 g/kg orally, whereas one group was given normal saline (10 mL/kg). Amongst these was mortification, strength of grip, painful reaction, touch reaction, rightening action, urination, sweating, lacrimation, hyperactivity, alertness, grooming, and corneal reflex the behavioral changes and response characteristics that were seen and documented at the hours are 1, 2, 4, 6, 12, 24, and 48.²¹

Anti-anxiety activity modes:

The test animals were split into 5 groups, each carrying Six rats, in order to assess the anxiolytic action in all of the exercises. Normal saline (10 mL/kg, oral) was given to the control group, while diazepam (5 mg/kg orally) was administered for the standard group. *Aconitum ferox* was given oral for all three treatment groups at 200, 300, and 500 mg/kg, respectively.

Elevated Plus Maze (EPM)

It stood 50 cm tall and had two arms that were open, each 50 cm by 10 cm, or two that closed, each 50 cm by 10 cm, with sides 50 cm high. The limbs with each kind were oriented toward one another. Infrared beams and sensors were part of the system to track arm movement for four minutes. Furthermore, a third party in the next room utilized a video link to observe rat. With this arrangement, entrance attempts into the open arms may be recorded, plus avoidance behaviors like the extended attend posture, in which the rat stretches forward before returning to its initial position. The drugs were given oral over an hour before to the tests. The longevity of the anxiolytic-like effects of an oral dosage of 10 mg/kg of Diazepam was evaluated in a follow-up trial. After injection, rats were evaluated every one, two, three, and six hours.²²

Light/Dark Box Test

The light/dark box apparatus was made up of a rectangular Plexiglas box measuring 44 cm in length, 21 cm in width, and 21 cm in height. It was separated into two equal-sized compartments by a barrier including a tiny aperture of 7 cm by 7 cm, which allowed the animals to freely travel between the two compartments. A 60 W white light was utilized to create an unpleasant atmosphere in one chamber and a safe, dark environment in the other. Saw dust covered the equipment floor, which was cleaned in between sessions to prevent olfactory signals.²³

Astrophotometer Test

The actophotometer (digital, Medcraft Electromedical Pvt. Ltd.) was used to measure spontaneous locomotor activity. The apparatus consists of a Perspex box with a grid floor and photocells. The movement of the animal interrupts the photocell beams and is recorded as activity counts. Each rat was placed individually in the apparatus for a 5-minute session, and the total activity counts were recorded. The apparatus was cleaned with 70% ethanol between sessions to avoid olfactory cues.

Rotarod Test

The rotarod apparatus (UGO Basile, Italy) was used to assess motor coordination and balance. The apparatus consists of a rotating rod (3 cm diameter) divided into five compartments by disks. The rotation speed can be adjusted and the time spent on the rod before falling is recorded. Rats were given a training session on the rotarod at a constant speed of 10 rpm for 2 minutes on the day before the actual test. On the testing day, each rat was placed on the rotating rod at a speed of 20 rpm, and the latency to fall was recorded. Each rat was given three trials with a 10-minute inter-trial interval.²⁴

Antidepressant activity:

The experimental animals were split into 5 groups of six rats per to examine the antidepressant effect across all tests. Orally normal saline (10 mL/kg) was given to the control group, whereas oral imipramine/ diazepam (10 mg/kg /5mg/kg) is administered for the standard group. *Aconitum ferox* was given oral for the three treatment groups at doses in 200, 300, and 500 mg/kg, respectively.

Despair swim test: Each rat was placed in a glass container (25 cm by 12 cm by 25 cm) filled to the top with fresh water and kept at 25°C. All the rats were moving around quite a bit at first, but in some time they relaxed in a familiar stillness. As a rat floated in the water motionless, just moving slightly to maintain its head above the surface, it was deemed immobile. A 5-minute test period was used to record the total immobility. We evaluated in several groups of rats the effect during the administration of drugs on the length of immobility.²⁵

Tail Suspension Test (TST)

The wooden chamber of the TST device measured 70 cm in height. At a height of 60 cm above the floor or 10 cm above the apparatus's top, a rod was installed between the chamber's side walls. Adhesive tape was placed one inch from the tip of the animals' tails and used to hang them from the rod. Twenty-four hours before to the final test session, the animals received a 15-minute pretest. The animals received their group treatments immediately following the pretest, six hours before to the final test, and thirty minutes prior to the final test. Each animal was separately suspended with a rod for the final test session, which lasted five minutes. After the last dosage had been administered for thirty minutes or 24 hours after the initial test session. Every animal's period of immobility was recorded for five minutes. When a mouse hung still on a pole without making any attempt to free itself, it was said to be immobile.²⁶

Biochemical investigation²⁷**HDL Cholesterol Testing**

To perform the assay, label tubes for the reagent blank, calibrator, and test samples. Add 450 µl of Reagent 1 to each tube. For the reagent blank, add 5 µl of distilled water, and for the calibrator and test samples, add 5 µl of the respective sample or calibrator. Mix the contents of each tube and incubate them for 5 minutes at 37°C. After incubation, add 150 µl of Reagent 2 to each tube, mix again, and incubate for another 5 minutes at 37°C. The absorbance of each tube is measured at a primary wavelength of 578 nm and a secondary wavelength of 670 nm using a colorimeter or biochemistry analyser. Calculated with the formula.

$$\text{HDL-C (mg/dl)} = \left(\frac{\text{Abs. of Test (T)}}{\text{Abs. of Calibrator (C)}} \right) \times \text{Concentration of Calibrator}$$

Triglycerides:

The intensity of this dye, measured at 505 nm (500-540 nm), is proportional to the concentration of triglycerides in the sample. For reagent preparation, allow the reagent bottle and AQUA-4 (supplied in the kit) to reach room temperature (15-30°C). Add the indicated amount of AQUA-4 to the reagent bottle, swirl to dissolve, and let it stand for 10 minutes at room temperature without shaking vigorously. The reconstituted reagent is stable until the expiry date at 2-8°C. The stability of the samples is 2 days at 20-25°C, 7 days at 4-8°C, and at least 1 year at -20°C. Contaminated specimens should be discarded. The assay procedure involves pipetting 1000 µl of working reagent into tubes marked for blank, standard, and test

$$\text{Triglycerides (mg/dl)} = \left(\frac{\text{Abs. of Test}}{\text{Abs. of Standard}} \right) \times \text{Concentration of Standard}$$

S.G.P.T Kit:

For reagent reconstitution, the contents of Aqua-4 are added to the SGPT reagent and swirled to dissolve without shaking vigorously. The reagent remains stable for 30 days at 2-8°C after reconstitution. For specimen collection, use non-haemolysed serum or plasma, following NCCLS procedures. The test's assay parameters include a kinetic mode at 340 nm wavelength, with sample and reagent volumes specified, and a total reaction volume of 1000 µL. The procedure involves pipetting the working reagent and test sample, mixing well, and aspirating for measurement.

$$\text{IU/L} = \frac{(\Delta A/\text{min}) \times TV \times 10^3}{SV \times \text{Absorptivity} \times P}$$

SGOT Kit: The reagent composition for Reagent 1 includes 12 mmol/L of 2-Oxoglutarate, 200 mmol/L of L-Aspartate, 545 U/L of MDH, 0.18 mmol/L of NADH (Yeast), and 80 mmol/L of Tris Buffer at pH 7.8. It also contains EDTA (5.0 mmol/L) and non-reactive fillers and stabilizers. Reconstitution of the reagents requires mixing the reagent bottle and Aqua-4 as specified on the label and swirling gently to dissolve. The unopened reagents are stable until the expiration date when stored at 2-8°C. Once reconstituted, the reagent is stable for 30

days at 2-8°C, with the discard criteria if it turns turbid or absorbance is below 0.8 at 340 nm against distilled water.

Cholesterol: Once the reagents are prepared, the assay procedure begins by pipetting into tubes marked as Blank, Standard, and Test. For each tube, add 1000 µl of Working Reagent. Then, add 20 µl of distilled water to the Blank tube, 20 µl of Standard to the Standard tube, and 20 µl of the rat serum sample to the Test tube. Mix the contents well and incubate the tubes at 37°C for 10 minutes. After incubation, aspirate the blank and read the absorbance of the Standard and Test samples at 505 nm on a bichromatic analyzer, using the blank as a reference

Histology:

Following the course of therapy, the animals were killed, and their brains were taken out for histopathological analysis. After all organs were quickly fixed in 10% buffered formalin, the following steps were used to make the histological cuts: fixation, dehydration, paraffin embedding, microtome sections, and hematoxylin-eosin-Safran (HES) colouring. Ultimately, an optical microscope was used to examine the incisions.²⁸

Result:

Phytochemical analysis:

Results of the phytochemical screening of the ethanolic Extract of *Aconitum ferox* leaves.

Table no.1 Result of Phytochemical screening

S no.	Phytochemical	Ethanol	Chloroform	Methanol
1.	Alkaloids	+	+	-
2.	Glycosides	+	+	+
3.	Carbohydrates	+	-	+
4.	Tannins	+	-	+
5.	Steroids	+	-	-
6.	Proteins and Amino Acids	-	-	+
7.	Resins	+	+	+
8.	Flavonoids	+	+	+

Note: (+) = Indicates the presence and (-) = Indicates the absence of the tested group

TLC Analysis of Plant Extract:

Chromatography using thin layers the produced TLC plates displayed spots that matched the reference quercetin and ethanol extract of *Aconitum ferox* when they got saturated with iodine vapours (Fig. 1.1A). The results of the ethanol extraction of *Aconitum ferox* from the plates produced under ultraviolet (UV) are shown in (Fig. 1.1 B,C). Additionally, the concentrated test sample's thin layer chromatogram.

Figure no 1.1A. TLC of ethenolic extract,B,C, TLC of *Aconitum ferox* of ethenolic extract under the UV trans illuminator

IR spectrum:

Figure no. 1.2 IR Spectra of *Aconitum ferox*

Table no 1. Spectra of IR peaks

OH	3402.35
Methoxy (O-CH ₃)	2923.98
Amide (CO-NH)	1619.32
Ether	1218.79
C-C	774.17
C-O	165.09
C-H	1383.68

Acute Toxicity:

Aconitum ferox was shown to be safe in rat acute toxicology tests out to a level of 300 mg/kg. Up to a dosage of 300 mg/kg, no signs of toxicity and mortality was observed. However, a single rat died as a result of acute exposure in a 500 mg/kg dosage of plant extract.

Anti-anxiety activity of *Aconitum ferox*:

EPM Test:

In the treatment groups that received the doses of 300 mg/kg or 500 mg/kg of *Aconitum ferox*, there was a significant increase in the time spent in open arms (99.83 ± 17.11 seconds and 107.83 ± 12.36 seconds) or a decrease in a time spent in closed arms of EPM (200.16 ± 17.11 seconds and 192.16 ± 12.36 seconds). The results of *Aconitum ferox* 500 mg/kg were highly significant shows in figure no 1.3, 1.4

Figure no 1.3 Open Arm time (s) spend

Figure no 1.4 Closed Arm time (s) spend

Light Dark test:

Rat's average time spent in the light box increased or dark box time spend is decrease as a result of *Aconitum ferox*. The average time spent in light was recorded as 90.66 ± 16.30 seconds, 103.16 ± 17.9 seconds, & 124.8 ± 18.8 seconds for the treatment groups of *Aconitum ferox* at 200, 300, and 500 mg/kg, respectively. The average time spent in the dark was recorded as 192.6 ± 22.49 seconds, 200.16 ± 17.1 seconds, and 161.16 ± 18.0 seconds shows in figure no 1.4, 1.5.

Figure no 1.4 Light area time (s) spend

Figure no 1.5 Dark area time(s) spend

Actophotometer:

By reducing the amount time that was spent in the treatment group in the actophotometer (42.16 ± 6.30 seconds & 38.16 ± 4.34 seconds), *Aconitum ferox* shown the doses of 300 mg/kg & 500 mg/kg has considerable anxiolytic potential. The outcomes of *Aconitum ferox* 500 mg/kg were very important shows in figure no 1.6

Figure no 1.6 time(s) spend in actophotometer

Rota Road: By increasing the duration spent on the rota rod (45.50 ± 8.8 seconds & 52.66 ± 7.59 seconds), *Aconitum ferox* showed the given doses of 100 mg/kg & 200 mg/kg had significant anxiolytic effect in all of the groups who received them. The outcomes of *Aconitum ferox* 200 mg/kg were very important shows in figure no 1.7

Figure no 1.7 time(s) spend in Rota rod

Antidepressant test:

The control group's swimming exercise lasted ten minutes (600 seconds), during which the rat in the standard and treatment groups alternated between being mobile and immobile. In FST, imipramine significantly shortened the time spent moving and lengthened the time spent immobile.

FST TEST:

Aconitum ferox caused a decrease in the length of movement and an increase in the duration of mobility. Rats administered 300 and 500 mg/kg of *Aconitum ferox* were found to be immobile for 53.83 ± 7.96 seconds ($P < .01$) and 33.33 ± 4.08 seconds ($P < .001$), respectively, and mobile for 246.16 ± 7.96 seconds ($P < .01$) and 266.66 ± 4.08 seconds ($P < .001$), respectively figure no 1.8

A)

B)

Figure no 1.8 A, B Average time of immobility & Mobility

Effects of the crude extract of *Aconitum ferox* and Imipramine on duration of mobility and immobility in forced swim test. All values are given in mean \pm SEM. N = 6. $P < .001$ (***) and $P < .05$ (**) as compared to control (ANOVA followed by Turkey test).

TST Test:

Comparing imipramine to the control group, both the length of mobility and the duration of immobility were considerably reduced ($P < .001$). The *Aconitum ferox* 200 mg/kg results showed strong statistical significance ($P < .001$). The length of increased mobility and duration of immobility decreased caused by varying *Aconitum ferox* dosages are summed up in figure no 1.9

A)

B)

Figure no 1.9 All values are given in mean \pm SEM. N = 6. $P < .001$ (***) and $P < .05$ (ns) as compared to control (ANOVA followed by Turkey test).

Biochemical estimation:

Cholesterol:

In the treatment groups that received the doses of 300 mg/kg or 500 mg/kg of *Aconitum ferox*, there was a significant increase at 670nm (4.13 ± 0.19 seconds and 3.76 ± 0.32 seconds). The results of *Aconitum ferox* 500 mg/kg were highly rise the level shows of absorbance in figure no 1.10

Figure no 1.10 Cholesterol absorbance in 670nm with diazepam

Triglycerides: Triglyceride level are absorbed with the diazepam standard drug in 670nm is showing significant effect of *Aconitum ferox* with different dosage 300, 500 mg/kg, high dose group is very effect full result are observed is 3.54 ± 0.2 , 3.72 ± 0.47 .

Figure no 1.11 Cholesterol absorbance in 670nm with diazepam

S.G.P.T: The significantly increase the SGPT value of test drug different dose 300, 500mg/kg with the comparison of control group result is observed in figure no 1.11 (8.65 ± 0.20 , 9.68 ± 0.39).

Figure no 1.12 SGPT level with diazepam

SGOT:The significantly increase the SGPT value of test drug different dose 300, 500mg/kg with the comparison of control group result is observed in figure no 1.12 (8.28 ± 0.61 , 10.52 ± 0.51).

Figure no 1.13 SGOT level with diazepam

HDL Cholesterol:

In the treatment groups that received the doses of 300 mg/kg or 500 mg/kg of *Aconitum ferox*, there was a significant increase at 670nm (10.67 ± 1.22 seconds and 14.73 ± 2.64 seconds). The results of *Aconitum ferox* 500 mg/kg were highly rise the level shows of absorbance in figure no 1.14

Figure no 1.14HDL cholesterol absorbed at 670nm with diazepam

Histology:

Biochemical and structural changes in the cerebral cortex were studied with histopathology to determine their relationship. Histopathological studies of the cerebral cortex exhausted with eosin and haematoxylin show that the shape of the neurons in the control group is standard. Anxiety and depressant for 15 hr causes the stroma to be swollen and the number of cells to grow. Few cells also had more cytoplasm, larger nuclei, and more, showing that giving Anxiety rats *Aconitum ferox* was an effective way to fix the damage to the cerebral cortex caused by Anxiety.

For Anxiety:

Figure no 1.15 Histology of Cerebral cortex part to identify of A (control group), B Standard drug(5mg/kg), C(200mg/kg) D (300mg/kg), E (500mg/kg)High dose of *Aconitum Ferox* is showed in D the antianxiety effect.

For Anti-depressant:

Figure no 1.16 Histology of Cerebral cortex part to identify of A (control group), B Standard drug(10mg/kg), C(200mg/kg) D (300mg/kg), E (500mg/kg) High dose of *Aconitum Ferox* is showed in E the ant-depressant effect.

Neurotoxicity Rat Histology:In the high dose of our plant extract 500mg/kg given by orally showing toxicity in day 11 of this schedule treatment in only one rat. we are examining through the histology for the conformation of toxicity showing figure no 1.17

Figure no 1.17 Acute toxicity in 11 day of treatment with 500mg/kg dose orally

Safety Profile and Therapeutic Window

A critical finding of this study is the dose-dependent toxicity profile of *A. ferox* crude extract. While 200–300 mg/kg demonstrated anxiolytic and antidepressant effects without mortality, administration of 500 mg/kg resulted in acute toxicity and death in one animal by day 11. This aligns with the documented toxicity of

Aconitum species, which contain diterpenoid alkaloids (aconitine, mesaconitine, hypaconitine) that exert neurotoxic and cardiotoxic effects via voltage-gated sodium channel modulation (Chan, 2014). The narrow therapeutic window observed—where anxiolytic effects and toxicity occur at proximate doses—highlights the risk-benefit paradox of crude aconite preparations. Traditional processing methods (decoction, soak-processing) reduce alkaloid toxicity while preserving bioactivity; future investigations should employ such detoxified fractions rather than crude extracts to improve safety margins.

Conclusion:

The present study demonstrates that *Aconitum ferox* root extract exhibits dose-dependent anxiolytic and antidepressant-like effects in rodent models, with significant activity observed at 200–300 mg/kg. However, acute toxicity observed at 500 mg/kg (including mortality in one subject) indicates a narrow therapeutic window, characteristic of aconite alkaloids. While these findings support the ethnopharmacological use of *A. ferox* in traditional medicine, the therapeutic potential is constrained by neurotoxicity at higher doses. Future studies must focus on detoxification protocols, alkaloid fractionation, or structural modification to isolate anxiolytic constituents from cardiotoxic/neurotoxic diterpenoid alkaloids. The present data caution against unsupervised use of crude *A. ferox* preparations and emphasize the necessity of rigorous dose standardization before therapeutic development.

Abbreviations:

DSM	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual
GAD	Generalized Anxiety Disorder
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
EPM	elevated plus maze
NS	normal saline
DZP	diazepam
ANOVA	analysis of variance
SEM	standard error of mean
G	grams
S	second
Kg	kilogram
Mg	milligram
ml	milliliter

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